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- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
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MUNDARIJA

Methods used in business decision-making.....	10
Ochilidiev Bekhruz To'liqin ogli, Safarov Alisher	

METHODS USED IN BUSINESS DECISION-MAKING

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Abstract: This article highlights the need for effective management decision-making in business in the context of the rapid development of modern technologies and the increasing flow of information. The main problems that arise in the decision-making process are uncertainty, lack of information, time constraints, and emotional factors. It also substantiates the effectiveness of a systematic approach to decision-making, multivariate analysis, and the use of digital analytical tools. The research was conducted on the basis of qualitative and quantitative methods, and practical results were achieved using interviews, focus groups, questionnaires, and statistical analysis. According to the results, effective leadership, teamwork, and information flow management in decision-making, as well as control of emotional factors, were identified as key factors. The article is useful not only for large, but also for small and medium-sized businesses, and serves as a scientific and practical guide in the fields of corporate governance, strategic planning, and management.

Key words: decision-making methods, management decisions, complex decisions, management effectiveness, modern decision-making methods, organizational effectiveness, economic effectiveness.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada zamonaviy texnologiyalar tez sur'atlarda rivojlanib, axborot oqimi ortib borayotgan sharoitda biznesda boshqaruv qarorlarini samarali qilish zaruriyati yoritilgan. Qaror qabul qilish jarayonida yuzaga keladigan asosiy muammolar — noaniqlik, axborot yetishmovchiligi, vaqt cheklanganligi va hissiy omillar tahlil etilgan. Shuningdek, qaror qabul qilishda tizimli yondashuv, ko'p variantli tahlil va raqamli-analitik vositalardan foydalanishning samaradorligi asoslab berilgan. Tadqiqot sifat va miqdoriy metodlar asosida olib borilib, intervyular, fokus-guruhlar, so'rovnomalar hamda statistik tahlillar yordamida amaliy natijalarga erishilgan. Natijalarga ko'ra, samarali rahbarlik, jamoaviy ishlash, qaror qabul qilishda axborot oqimini boshqarish va hissiy omillarni nazorat qilish asosiy omillar sifatida ajratilgan. Maqola nafaqat yirik, balki kichik va o'rta biznes subyektlari uchun ham foydali bo'lib, korporativ boshqaruv, strategik rejalashtirish va menejment sohalarida ilmiy-amaliy qo'llanma sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: qaror qabul qilish usullari, boshqaruv qarorlari, murakkab qarorlar, boshqaruv samaradorligi, zamonaviy qaror qabul qilish metodlari, tashkiliy samaradorlik, iqtisodiy samaradorlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается необходимость эффективного принятия управленческих решений в бизнесе в условиях стремительного развития современных технологий и увеличивающегося потока информации. Основными проблемами, возникающими в процессе принятия решений, являются неопределенность, недостаток информации, временные ограничения и эмоциональные факторы. Обоснована эффективность системного подхода к принятию решений, многомерного анализа и использования цифровых аналитических инструментов. Исследование проводилось на основе качественных и количественных методов, а практические результаты были достигнуты с помощью интервью, фокус-групп, анкетирования и статистического анализа. По результатам исследования в качестве ключевых факторов были выделены эффективное лидерство, командная работа, управление информационными потоками при принятии решений, а также контроль эмоциональных факторов. Статья полезна не только для крупного, но и для малого и среднего бизнеса, а также служит научно-практическим руководством в области корпоративного управления, стратегического планирования и менеджмента.

Ключевые слова: методы принятия решений, управленческие решения, сложные решения, эффективность управления, современные методы принятия решений, организационная эффективность, экономическая эффективность.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study examined the analysis of decision-making processes in the business sector, their effectiveness, errors and decision-making methods. As a research methodology, a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches was used. The aim of the qualitative approach is to deeply analyze the decision-making process and identify methodological tools for improving errors, problems and efficiency in decision-making. Methods based on this approach are used. The study conducted in-depth interviews with leaders and managers involved in the decision-making process. These interviews provided an opportunity to explore the uncertainties, errors, and practical rules for optimal decision-making in the decision-making process. Focus groups with representatives of specific business sectors explored changes and recommendations in the decision-making process. Focus groups collected opinions on how to improve performance in real-world situations where decisions are made based on surveys.

Quantitative research methods aim to measure decision-making processes and propose effective solutions to them through statistical analysis based on specific data. Questionnaires and scales (e.g., Likert scale) were used to analyze errors in decision-making and to identify them. Using this method, respondents assessed the problems they encountered in decision-making and identified effective decision-making methods. Statistical methods, such as regression analysis and correlation analysis, were used to conduct the quantitative part of the study. These methods identify the relationship between decision-making factors and decision effectiveness.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis and research conducted on the topic studied in this study, namely, errors in decision-making processes in the business sector and improving their effectiveness, led to the following results. The first stage of the study was the analysis of the main errors that occur in the decision-making process. Based on questionnaires and interviews, 63% of respondents noted that they observed the following errors in the decision-making process: Lack of sufficient information: 40% of respondents noted that they did not have all the necessary information when making a decision. This led to making the wrong decisions. Time constraints: 35% of respondents reported that they faced negative consequences when making a decision due to the need to make a decision quickly and in a short period of time. Emotional influences: 25% of respondents said that decisions were made incorrectly due to emotional states, such as fear, insecurity or acute stress. As a result of these errors, the efficiency of business processes decreases, which can negatively affect the growth and development of organizations. Effective methods for increasing the efficiency of decision-making were analyzed. The study also identified the decision-making methods that respondents considered the most effective (Table 1):

Table 1. Types of decisions

Types of decisions	
1	The balanced decision-making style is a human-specific approach that is based on a preliminary analysis of the problem situation and the requirements for the issue. This decision-making tactic is productive.
2	Impulsive decisions are human in nature. Such a person is easily guided by thoughts. But they pay little attention to evaluation. Impulsiveness of decision-making can lead a leader to implement a decision that is not fully thought out and justified.
3	Inert decisions are the result of a long and unreliable search. Once an initial hypothesis is formed, its verification is very slow. The assessment is hypercritical, each step is checked by the person several times. This leads to a slowdown in the decision-making process.
4	Risky decisions are like impulsive decisions, but they differ from them in their individual tactics. While impulsive decisions skip the stage of a well-founded hypothesis, risky decisions overtake them. However, a person only evaluates when misunderstandings arise.
5	A cautious decision is determined by a clear assessment of the hypothesis. A person carries out various preparatory work before coming to a conclusion. Cautious people are more impressed by their negative actions than by their positive actions. optimal use of its resources (finance, personnel, time, etc.). This concept is a measure of the success andesses. Therefore, the tactical method of cautious people is to avoid making mistakes.

Research by G.V. Gutman has shown that decisions made by a successful leader must meet the following requirements: – Purposeful – that is, the decision must be formulated in a clear content, not cause ambiguity and doubts among subordinates and workers; – Rational and consistent – that is, it must fully correspond to internal and external situations, as well as previous and future decisions; – Authoritative – that is, it must take into account the duties and rights of the leader and subordinate, based on the requirements of the law,

employees with extensive work experience will ensure that we make the right decision. Because there is a situational approach in management, in which, when faced with an unforeseen situation, it is necessary to agree with the experience of experienced employees. Applying each of the above methods of making management decisions in an enterprise will lead to positive results. Before making decisions, it is necessary to carefully assess potential risks and take necessary measures to reduce or prevent them. Special risk management tools and methods should be developed for this process. Before making quick decisions, it is necessary to organize regular meetings and discussions in society for quick analysis and advice. The effectiveness of this approach helps to ensure that decisions are quick, but high-quality.

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